

An Empirical Study of Socio-Economic and Health Conditions of Yanadi Women in Nellore, Andhra Pradesh

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Abstract:- India is a sizable nation with a great deal of diversity. Scheduled Tribes are essential to preserving the diversity of the nation. Women from the Yanadi tribe are among those with a distinctive culture and way of life. Yanadi women's social, economic, and cultural problems are deteriorating both their circumstances and the country's progress. To better the lives of scheduled women in India and Andhra, the government adopted a number of policies. The Yanadi women, however, required to be the focus of additional policies and programs for their development as the current initiatives are insufficient to completely transform their situation. The paper aims to shed light on the socio-economic and health conditions of Yanadi women in particular in the Nellore, district of Andhra Pradesh.

Keywords:- Scheduled Tribe, Yanadi Women, Culture, Socio-Economic, Health Status.

“A social group with territorial affiliation, endogamous with no specialization of functions ruled by tribal officers hereditary or otherwise, united in language or dialect recognizing social distance with other tribes or castes”.

- D.N. Majumdar.

I. INTRODUCTION

India is a nation made up of several tribes, civilizations, and ethnic groupings. Everyone tends to believe that a tribe is a homogeneous group of people, but this is not the case. Instead, a tribe is a heterogeneous group of people.

Adivasi, a tribe whose name translates to "original inhabitant". The Adivasis are original inhabitants of Indian subcontinent (Robert Harrison Barnes 1995)¹. India is unquestionably a nation of tribes. India is home to more than 84.4 million people and contains the world's largest population of tribal people. Most Adivasis continue to live below the poverty line because they still rely on traditional livelihoods including subsistence farming, fishing in small ponds, and hunting. The indigenous people of India each have their own unique culture, religion, and social mores. While certain tribal groups in India have assimilated into society, most of the tribes still adhere to their original cultures.

A tribe in traditional cultures is a group of families united by social, economic, religious, or blood ties and sharing a same culture and dialect. A tribe has some specific characteristics, and which make a tribe a unique social organization with a whole different culture. Tribes usually have their own political organizations. States with sizable Adivasi populations include Telangana, Madhya Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh, Jharkhand, Gujarat, Chhattisgarh, Odisha, Gujarat, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, etc. Scheduled Tribes make up 8.6% of the population of India, as per the recent Census. Only 2.8% of the indigenous population inhabits urban areas, while rural areas make up 11.3% of the total. India has roughly 550 different tribes. There are around 700 tribal tribes in India, including 75 Particularly Vulnerable Tribal tribes (PVTGs), according to the 1951 census³. As per the report, the largest tribal group in India is the Gonds. Odisha has 62 different tribal communities which is the highest to any state in India. Andamanese are the smallest tribe, with only 19 individuals. In Haryana, Punjab, Chandigarh, Delhi, and Puducherry, there are no notified tribes.

Currently, 32 lakh tribals, 50 lakh nomads, and other disadvantaged groups living in Andhra Pradesh. Their habitat stretches from the Srikakulam district to the Khammam district and Godavari districts all the way up to the north-east to the Adilabad region along the coastal and mountain strip of the Bay of Bengal. The state's forested and hilly regions are home to most of the Andhra Pradesh's tribes.

Yanadi are one of the 33 tribes in Andhra. They are predominant in Nellore, Andhra. Yanadi live in symbiosis with non-tribals. Their population according to 2011 census reports is **5, 33,746** in Andhra Pradesh. (Dr. B Vijayasree 2018)⁴. The Yanadi are a small society made up primarily of nuclear families. They coexist alongside the families of their kin, which is another distinctive aspect of their community. They rely on primary jobs to support their economy. Women's unpaid work is rarely recorded in official work. (Ravi Babu J and Dr. Dhanalakshmi)⁵. Currently, there are several health issues that Yanadi women in India face.

➤ *Objectives of the Paper:*

- To assess the socioeconomic standing of Telangana's and Andhra Pradesh's tribal communities.
- To research the schemes and programs for the Yanadi tribe in Andhra.

II. METHODOLOGY

➤ *Sample Design*

The current study was carried out in the Nellore district to evaluate Yanadi's socioeconomic status. Four revenue divisions, including Nellore, Kandukuru, Athmakuru, and Kavali, make up the Nellore district. Three Revenue divisions were chosen for the study out of the four. Four mandals from each of the three revenue divisions chosen for the study. 300 samples were taken from the Nellore district, 30 from each chosen mandal.

➤ *Data collection*

Both primary and secondary data are used to support the present study. In order to gather information about the socioeconomic status and the issues facing women in the Yanadi tribe, the researchers used primary data and a pre-structured interview schedule.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

➤ *Age of the Respondents*

It deals with the socioeconomic analysis and interpretation of the data gathered from the field, as well as the biographical information of the sample beneficiaries and their ancestry. Religion, caste, age, degree of literacy, marital status, family size, assets, occupation, and other significant socioeconomic factors are covered. The major goal of the study is to assess the socioeconomic circumstances of the Yanadi tribe.

Table 1 Age of the Respondents

S. No.	Age	Frequency	Percentage
1	< - 20	19	6.33
2	20 - 30	38	12.66
3	30 - 40	112	37.33
4	40 – 50	98	32.66
5	50 – above	33	11.00
TOTAL		300	100.00

Source: Field Survey

The age distribution of respondents from the Yanadi tribal sample is shown in Table 1 below. Five age categories have been created to make additional analysis easier. According to the table, there are 12.66 percent and 37.33 percent of people in the age categories ranging from 20 to 30 and 30 to 40, respectively. About 32.6 percent of the population is between the ages of 40 and 50, and the remaining 11.0 percent is over the age of 50. Because of this, the majority of homes have a head of household who is between the ages of 30 and 40, and the average mean age of the households is 44.73 years.

➤ *Education of the Respondents*

Table 2 Education of the Respondents

S. No	Education	Frequency	Percent
1	Illiterate	128	42.66
2	Primary	116	38.66
3	Secondary	44	14.66
4	Above secondary	12	4.00
Total		300	100

Source: Field Survey

Women can only be empowered when they receive an education. It is thought that education fosters independence, confidence, and understanding. Women who lack literacy or education have a higher probability to be susceptible. The majority of responders had low levels of literacy development and schooling. Even still, it was discovered that 42.6% of respondents lacked literacy. A significant finding was that educated respondents reported having a high primary education rate of 38.6%. The remaining 14.6% are in secondary education, and 4% are SSC and above pupils. As a result, education isn't prioritized for the vast majority of Yanadi women.

➤ *Low salaries and Income*

The Yanadi tribe's women primarily work in traditional occupations, which results in very low-income levels. Some of the interviewees relied on subsistence agriculture, however, they infrequently receive surplus. According to this, the researcher discovered that Yanadi women's opinions on low earnings or wages have been collected on a five-point scale.

Table 3 Women's perceptions of Low Income and Wages

S. No.	Perceptions	Frequency	%	Weighted Average
1	Strongly agree	210	70.00	0.91
2	Agree	63	21.00	
3	Can't say	12	4.00	
4	Disagree	9	3.00	
5	Strongly disagree	6	2.00	
	Total	300	100.00	0.91

Source: Field Survey

The current table explored the Yanadi women's perception of their perceived low pay and gathered opinions on these parameters, which were then assessed and given in table 1.

Fig 1 Opinion on Low Income or Wages

The table showed how the respondents' opinions were broken down into five categories, including strongly agree, simply agree, can't say, disagree, and definitely disagree. 70 percent of the Yanadi women who responded strongly agreed, 21 percent just agreed, 3 percent claimed they disagreed, and 2 percent strongly disagreed with receiving poor pay or earnings.

The preceding table makes it quite evident that Yanadi women workers typically receive lesser pay because the majority of these workers are unaware of the Minimum

Wage Act or the equal pay system in India. In the research area, Yanadi women workers have consequently been paid less.

➤ *Homes of the Respondents:*

The opportunities of their earnings determine the economic position of the Yanadi women. The Yanadi tribe has few options to improve their financial situation, which limits their economic opportunities. The kind of house Yanadi lives in is a direct or indirect result of the families' financial resources.

Table 4 Percent Distribution of the Population's Homes by Type

S. No	Type of House	Frequency	Percentage
1	Kucha	189	63.00
2	Semi Pucca	57	19.00
3	Temporary constructions	54	18.00
	Total	300	100.00

Source: Field Survey

The respondent information regarding the homes built by Yanadi women was also gathered by the researcher. The type of the house of the sample is represented in the above table, which shows the sample's housing type, 63 percent of the sample's homes are kuchha 189, 19 percent are semi-puccas, and 54 percent of the population resides in temporary structures. Most of the homes have thatched roofs and are built like huts.

Fig 2 Percent Distribution of the Population's Homes by Type

➤ *Utilization of Services:*

The Yanadi women in the chosen sample region have access to services including Primary Health Centres, Aunganwadis, Public Distribution System, Primary Schools, and Government Hospitals.

Table 5 Utilization of Services by the Yanadi Tribes

S. No.	Utilization of services	Accessed (Yes)	Not Accessed (No)
1	PHC	124 (41.3)	176 (58.6)
2	Anganwadi	169 (56.3)	131 (43.6)
3	PDS	147 (49)	153 (51)
4	Primary Schools	112 (37)	188 (62.6)
5	Govt. Hospitals	96 (32)	204 (68)

Source: Field Survey

The Yanadi tribes' use of the services is apparent in Table 5. 41.3 percent of the sample uses services from the Primary Health Centre, whereas the remaining 58.6 percent does not. 49 percent of respondents utilised the Public Distribution System, while 51 percent did not utilise the PDS facility. Of the respondents, 56.3 percent send their children to Aunganwadis, and 43.6 percent do not send their children to the I.C.D.S. 62.6 percent of Yanadi mothers do not exhibit any desire to send their children to acquire a formal education, while 37 percent of them send their children to primary schools. Out of 300 people, 32 percent, or 96, use government hospital facilities; 204 percent, or 68 percent, do not.

➤ *Reasons for not using the Services:*

Table 6 Reasons for not using Services Available for Yanadi Women.

Reason	Frequency	Percentage
Taboos	68	22.6
Migration	106	35.3
Ignorance	112	37.3
Distance	56	18.6
Marginalization	184	61.3

Source: Field Survey

The yanadi tribal women community's reasons for not using the services are listed in the above table. Marginalisation is the main barrier for using the service (61.3%). They are marginalized because of their status as scavengers and frog-eating tribes, respectively. The study sample's next second top explanations were migration (35.3%) and ignorance of the services offered (37.3%). According to the study, one of the reasons people do not use services is because of tribal taboos (22.6%), while 18.6% of

the population claimed that the distance these services are from their homes as the reason, they do not use services.

IV. CONCLUSION

The Yanadi women of Nellore, A.P., have low literacy rates and poor income levels, which prevent them from developing socially or economically. Traditional health practises and a lack of access to healthcare and other services due to a variety of factors, including marginalisation, ignorance, and migration, are adversely affecting the health status of Yanadi women. The situation in the sample area has begun to improve in comparison to past years as a result of the government's various initiatives and strategies to improve the status of Yanadi women. The lives of the Yanadi women will rapidly undergo more transformation if this trend persists.

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